

production costs for hiring bullocks has fallen (from 35-39% earlier to 10-20% in 1984) due to increased use of machinery. □

ENVIRONMENT

Preliminary study on response of rice seedlings to enhanced UV-B radiation

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We assessed the effect of elevated UV-B radiation on morphological characteristics and physiological processes of rice seedlings. Differences among rice genotypes in growth characteristics in response to enhanced UV-B can provide important information on the mechanisms of and adaptation for UV-B tolerance.

Irrigated rice varieties IR30, IR45, IR64, and IR74 were tested in a randomized block design with three replications. Six pregerminated seeds were sown in 1-liter plastic pots containing 1.7 kg Maahas clay soil (Andaqueptic Haplaquoll). Fertilizer was applied at 0.4 g N, 0.04 g P, and 0.25 g K/kg soil.

Seedlings were raised in the greenhouse for 10 d, thinned to four plants

per pot, and transferred to a phytotron glasshouse for UV-B treatment.

UV-B radiation was supplied by two banks of 12-Q panel UV-B 313 sun-lamps. Lamps were filtered with cellulose acetate for UV-B treatment and with mylar film for control. Lamp height was 40 cm above the top of the plant canopy, as adjusted weekly. Weighted daily UV-B irradiance was about 19 kJ/m² biologically effective UV-B, using the generalized plant response action spectrum normalized at 300 nm.

Plants were irradiated daily for 6 h centered around solar noon for 4 wk. Glasshouse day/night temperature was 27/21°C and relative humidity was 70%.

UV-B treatment significantly decreased plant height, total leaf length of main culm, and total leaf dry weight of main culm (see table). Response varied among the test cultivars. IR74 was the most sensitive, IR64 the least. Cultivar differences were evident in shoot dry weight and total dry weight.

These results indicate that enhanced UV-B irradiation can alter rice plant morphology and (possibly) several physiological processes. The leaves appear to be the organ most sensitive to this environmental stress. The morphological changes in rice, however, do not appear to be as drastic as those reported for other C₃ species. □

Response of 4 rice varieties to 4 wk UV-B radiation at the seedling stage in the phytotron. IRRI, 1989.

Character	IR30	IR45	IR64	IR74
Plant height (cm)	—**	—**	—**	—*
Max root length/plant (cm)	—	+	—	—
Root volume/plant (cm ³)	+	—	—	—**
Tiller number/plant	+	—	+	—**
Leaf area/plant (cm ²)	—	—	—	—**
Leaf dry weight/plant (g)	—	—*	—	—**
Sheath dry weight/plant (g)	—	—	—	—**
Root dry weight/plant (g)	—	—	—	—**
Shoot dry weight/plant (g)	—	—*	—	—**
Dry weight/plant (g)	—	—*	—	—**
Specific leaf weight (mg/cm ²)	—	—	+	+
Relative growth rate (mg/g per d)	—	—*	—	—**
Net assimilation rate (g/m ² per d)	—	—	+	—**
Shoot-to-root ratio	+	—	+	—**
Total leaf length of main culm (cm)	—**	—**	—**	—*
Total leaf area of main culm (cm ²)	—	+	—	—
Total leaf dry weight of main culm (g)	—**	—*	—	—**

+ positive effect of UV-B. — negative effect of UV-B. * significant at 0.05 level. ** significant at 0.01 level.

ANNOUNCEMENT

ICAR celebrates 25 years of rice research

India's Directorate of Rice Research will mark 25 yr of work on rice with an international symposium in November 1990. Rice scientists from all over the world will participate in a three-day program that will include presentation of formal papers and poster sessions.

Four technical sessions are planned: research accomplishments and challenges, genetics and biotechnology, space and communication technology, and futurology.

The Directorate of Rice Research began as the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP) in 1965.

For information about the symposium, contact

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